

Mapping Boolean Logic with Protein-Based Colloids: A Microelectrode Array (MEA) Approach

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Abstract

Liquid-based and colloidal computing systems represent an emerging paradigm in unconventional computation, leveraging the unique physicochemical properties of fluids to enable novel information processing architectures. This paper investigates using egg albumen, an edible, biodegradable and bioresorbable natural protein matrix, as a functional medium for memfractance behaviour and Boolean logic implementation. We report the fabrication and electrical characterisation of albumen-based colloidal systems, revealing memfractor-like current-voltage (I–V) hysteresis, as well as conductance modulation through potentiation and depression using pulsed voltage stimuli. Microelectrode arrays (MEAs) were used to successfully extract Boolean logic operations from the colloids, confirming their computing capability. These findings demonstrate the suitability of egg albumen as a sustainable and biologically compatible computing substrate and introduce a novel approach to low-cost, environmentally friendly colloid computing systems. This research lays the groundwork for future biologically integrated electronics with logic processing capabilities.

Keywords:

Boolean gates, Unconventional Computing, Colloids, Proteins, Microelectrode arrays

1. Introduction

The field of unconventional computing has undergone significant transformation in recent years, with novel paradigms emerging that challenge conventional digital computation frameworks [1, 2, 3]. Contemporary research has demonstrated remarkable progress across multiple domains, including neuromorphic systems engineered at colloidal scales [4, 5, 6, 7], fluid-based logic operations [8, 9, 10], and liquid-state computational platforms [11, 12]. This evolu-

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tion builds upon a rich historical foundation spanning early hydraulic computing devices, mathematical fluid integrators, and chemical reaction-diffusion processors [13, 14, 15]. Modern implementations now encompass advanced systems such as liquid marble computers, fluidic logic gates, and colloidal neuromorphic architectures, collectively expanding the boundaries of information processing beyond traditional silicon-based approaches [16, 17, 18, 19].

The search for materials to mimic the behaviour of biological synapses has led researchers to explore a wide range of options, including inorganic compounds, perovskites, metal oxides, chalcogenides, and two-dimensional materials [20, 21, 22, 23, 24]. While these materials have potential, they are often difficult to synthesise, incompatible with biological systems, and financially expensive. This incompatibility raises environmental issues and limits practical applications. To tackle these issues, researchers are utilising natural resources such as proteins and plant-derived chemicals. These materials are generally more affordable, easily obtainable, and eco-friendly [25, 26, 27].

Egg albumen, a protein-rich material, is a promising candidate for electronic devices due to its abundance, biodegradability, and bioresorbability [28]. Comprising approximately 90% water and 10% proteins (albumins, mucoproteins, and globulins), egg albumen has been used to fabricate field-effect transistors (FETs) and memristors [29, 30]. These devices exhibit nonvolatile memory capabilities and potential for applications in lab-on-chip systems, highlighting egg albumen’s versatility in electronics [31]. Its environmental sustainability and natural origin position egg albumen as a viable material for developing innovative, eco-friendly electronic devices [32].

Advances in electrophysiological techniques have enabled simultaneous neural activity recording with multiple electrodes, facilitating studies of electrogenic cell function and structure within neuronal networks [33].

Microelectrode arrays (MEAs) offer significant benefits for diverse applications in biomedical and neuroscience research. These devices enable high-resolution, parallel recording of electrophysiological signals from numerous excitable cells, including neurons. Within neuroengineering, MEAs play a pivotal role in developing and testing neural prosthetics and brain-computer interfaces by providing essential electrophysiological data for effective neural interfacing and stimulation. In addition, they serve as powerful tools for investigating neuronal network dynamics, including information encoding, signal propagation, and collective computational processes. Such capabilities make MEAs indispensable for advancing our understanding of neural mechanisms underlying cognition, memory formation, and higher-order brain functions.

The electrical properties of colloidal proteins have not been previously studied using MEA technologies and may be implicated in a range of biological phenomena [34, 35]. Although different commercial tools for data analysis exist, their versatility and compatibility are often limited in particular when applied to unconventional computing substrates such as proteins. Consequently, we used a hardware interface designed and developed by our team for recording low-frequency activity using microelectrode arrays in this research [36].

To evaluate the computational potential of egg albumen, we experimentally

demonstrated Boolean logic operations within the colloidal medium. Binary input sequences were encoded through electrical stimulation of the liquid solution, while the corresponding output signals were captured using microelectrode array technology. The acquired electrical responses were subsequently analysed, categorised, and translated into equivalent logical expressions, establishing the material’s capability to perform fundamental computing operations.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Preparation of Albumen Colloids

Fresh hen eggs sourced from Morrisons were cracked, and the albumen was separated and sonicated to produce a homogeneous suspension.

2.2. Electrical Measurements

Current and voltage (I-V) characteristics of the albumen were obtained using a source meter (2450 Source Measure Unit, Keithley).

Conductance potentiation and depression were investigated using a pulse generator (Sanworks, Pulse Pal v2) using a series of 20 ± 5 V, 10 ms pulses. Voltage and current signals were acquired with a PC-based oscilloscope (Pico Technology, PicoScope 5442D).

A 50 mV (rms) was applied to measure the impedance of the albumen over a frequency of 20 Hz to 1 MHz using an Inductance-Capacitance-Resistance (LCR) meter (model 891, BK Precision Ltd, UK).

All electrical characterisation measurements were performed with specialised platinum/iridium-coated stainless steel probes (Spes Medica) under standard atmospheric conditions at 20 °C.

2.3. Micro-electrode arrays (MEAs)

Electrical recordings were made using 60 hard gold-plated MEAs (60EcoMEA-gr, Part No. 890805) with 60 electrodes (59 channels and 1 reference electrode) [36]. The multi-channel signals were subsequently recorded utilising a custom interface integrated with sigma-delta analogue-to-digital converter dataloggers at a sampling rate of 16 Hz (Pico Technologies, UK, ADC-24). This setup allowed for the recording of data from 59 single-ended electrode channels and a reference electrode (linked to GND). For MEA stimulation experiments the stimulation device and MEA shared ground connection.

The microelectrode array (MEA) consisted of single-ended electrodes arranged in grids of 6×8 and 2×6 , each electrode spaced 700 μm apart with a diameter of 100 μm . To deliver stimuli selectively and limit interference from external conditions, a plastic tube was placed over the electrodes, leaving only their tips exposed for recording (Fig. 1a).

2.4. Boolean expression extraction

Four-bit Boolean expressions were extracted from colloids by introducing binary strings $b_n \in \{0,1\}^4$. Each bit of these strings alternated every 15 s. Signals were encoded as bipolar pulses, where logical false corresponded to -5 V and logical true corresponded to 5 V.

Electrical signals were generated with an Arduino Uno R4 board (Arduino, Italy), interfaced via I2C to two MCP4728 12-bit quad-channel digital-to-analogue converters (DACs, Microchip Technology, USA), utilizing a 74HC595 multiplexer (Texas Instruments, USA). DAC outputs were amplified and level-shifted using circuits based on LM258AP operational amplifiers (Texas Instruments, USA), producing bipolar ± 5 V outputs. An IPS-4303 laboratory DC power supply (ISO-TECH, Taiwan) provided stable positive and negative voltage rails. A photo of the stimuli generation setup is shown in Fig. 2a.

Four input probes, 10 μm diameter platinum/iridium-coated stainless steel, from the apparatus were inserted into the colloid, and the resulting potentials were recorded using the microelectrode array (MEA) (Figs. 1b and 2b). The measurement was repeated 10 times.

Figure 1: Plan view of (a) MEA interface board, (b) experimental setup with four ADC loggers

Figure 2: a) A custom-designed apparatus was employed to apply 4-bit strings to the egg albumen. b) Schematic of applying the step waves and measuring with the MEA.

The measured output signals were subsequently threshold-classified from 5% to 90% V_{peak} by assigning a logical true if the absolute voltage exceeded the threshold and a logical false if it fell below, as illustrated in Fig. 3. These threshold-classified outputs were then used to create a truth table, which was subsequently converted into a Boolean expression.

Figure 3: Pulse classification procedure for 4-bit string input, adapted from [10].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Current-Voltage Measurements

Current-voltage (I-V) measurements were conducted to characterise the electrical properties of the albumen colloid. Fig. 4a shows the current response and applied voltage over time during cyclic DC sweeps between -5 V and 5 V at a scan rate of 2 V s^{-1} .

The I-V curves exhibit a hysteresis loop, indicative of systems with memory [37, 38, 39]. The colloidal device demonstrates consistent bipolar switching, with set and reset transitions under positive and negative bias, respectively. This nonlinear switching profile is supported by an observed decrease in current amplitude over successive cycles, suggesting partial charge trapping or ionic drift, as reported in other protein-based memristive systems [39].

Under positive bias, the current in the colloidal suspension increases nonlinearly, switching the device from a high-resistance state (HRS) to a low-resistance state (LRS) in a process termed the set operation. Conversely, under negative bias, the current decreases, transitioning the device from the LRS to the HRS, known as the reset operation.

Proteins in albumen, such as albumin, lysozyme, and ovomucin, remain folded under native conditions and are associated with mineral ions, including iron (Fe), potassium (K), and sodium (Na) [28]. The electrical modulation of the colloid may result from conformational rearrangements and ionic movement within the protein matrix. The presence of metal ions such as K^+ , Na^+ , and Fe^{2+} , bound to albumen proteins like ovalbumin and ovotransferrin, can act as charge carriers or contribute to redox reactions essential for resistance modulation [40].

This behaviour demonstrates the device’s bipolar switching capability, where its conductivity can be modulated by the polarity of the applied external bias. Furthermore, repeated measurements reveal a gradual decrease in absolute current over multiple sweep cycles, while the average hysteresis loop retains its characteristic shape over five cycles. This highlights the device’s capacity for controlled resistance modulation and voltage-dependent conductance adjustments, enabling it to perform classification tasks within the experimental framework [18].

3.2. Potentiation and Depression

To evaluate the computing potential of the device, potentiation and depression experiments were carried out to demonstrate its ability to mimic artificial synapse behaviour. For these tests, the pulse amplitudes were configured to 5 V for the set operation and -5 V for the reset operation, with each pulse having a duration of 10 ms . Conductance measurements were performed using a 50 mV pulse [18]. Figure 5 illustrates the recorded conductance values during the application of 20 sequential set and reset pulses within the colloidal suspension. The results indicate that the device exhibits effective potentiation (a gradual increase in conductance) and depression (a gradual decrease in conductance).

Figure 4: (a) Measured current and input voltage versus time for the albumen colloid. (b) Current and voltage characteristics of the albumen colloid for a 2 V s^{-1} scan rate.

These findings confirm that the device successfully replicates the potentiation and depression dynamics observed in biological synapses.

A significant achievement of this study lies in the successful emulation of synaptic potentiation and depression through pulse-driven conductance modulation. The device demonstrated a stable increase and decrease in conductance across repeated $\pm 5 \text{ V}$ pulses, effectively simulating long-term potentiation (LTP) and long-term depression (LTD), the electrophysiological basis for learning and memory in biological systems [18]. Such dynamics are essential for realising spiking neural networks (SNNs), and our results underscore the potential of albumen colloids for use in synapse-like devices capable of adaptive learning.

Compared with traditional inorganic memristors based on metal oxides or chalcogenides, the use of a biocompatible matrix offers clear advantages in terms of sustainability, ease of fabrication, and integration into soft electronics and implantable interfaces. However, the temporal stability and repeatability of plasticity under extended cycling remain important avenues for further investigation.

3.3. Impedance spectroscopy

Figure 6 illustrates the impedance modulus response of the egg albumen colloid as a function of frequency. At low frequencies ($1 - 10 \text{ Hz}$), a high impedance ($2 \text{ k}\Omega$) is observed, likely due to polarisation effects and interfacial phenomena within the colloid. At these low frequencies, ions and charged species within the colloid have sufficient time to migrate and accumulate at interfaces or boundaries, leading to a higher resistance to the flow of alternating current. The minor fluctuations observed in the low-frequency region could be indicative of complex interfacial phenomena or the presence of multiple relaxation processes within the colloid [41].

As frequency ($10 \text{ Hz} - 100 \text{ kHz}$) increases, impedance modulus decreases significantly, showing that the influence of these polarisation mechanisms is de-

Figure 5: Potentiation and depression features of the colloid's conductance when applying a series of 20 ± 5 V, 10 ms pulses.

creasing. As the frequency rises, the periodic reversal of the applied electric field accelerates faster than the time required for these polarisation processes to fully develop. Consequently, the system's impedance modulus is reduced [42].

At frequencies above 100 kHz, the impedance modulus plateaus at a lower value (about 150Ω). This suggests that the intrinsic resistance and ionic conductivity of the bulk material become the dominant factors at these frequencies, where polarisation effects are less significant. The observed impedance response is characteristic of many colloidal systems. The high impedance at low frequencies can be associated with capacitive behaviour arising from interfacial polarisation, while the low impedance at high frequencies reflects the resistive component of the material [43, 19].

3.4. Boolean Gates

Low frequency recordings of deionised water (Millipore Milli-DI® water purification system, $15 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) with MEA interface and Pico ADC-24 data loggers is published in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068709>. Figure 7a presents the recorded electrical response of the albumen-based colloidal system to 4-bit binary inputs $b = \{0, 1\}^4$.

Figure 7b presents a waterfall plot of normalised voltages across the MEA, illustrating the spatial distribution of electrical activity within the colloidal material. The y -axis electrode indexing highlights variations in voltage dispersion, reflecting the system's spatial complexity and distributed signal processing capabilities.

The binarised classified responses were then arranged into truth tables to derive the minimal Sum-of-Products (SOP) Boolean expressions. The ten most frequently identified Boolean expressions, determined under different threshold configurations, are summarised in Table 1.

Analysis of Boolean expressions derived from the albumen-based colloid system (see Table 1) reveals that the most frequent logic pattern, $\neg a \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg c \wedge \neg d$,

Figure 6: The impedance modulus response of the egg albumen as a function of frequency.

occurred 433 times. This suggests a pronounced sensitivity of the system to complete input inactivity. The second most frequent expression, $a \vee d \vee \neg b \vee \neg c$, recorded 361 occurrences, indicating responsiveness to a combination of active and inactive input states.

Additionally, complex expressions involving both conjunction and disjunction, such as $(b \wedge c \wedge d \wedge \neg a) \vee (a \wedge c \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg d)$, were observed with notable frequency. This indicates the colloid’s capacity to support multivariate logic evaluation and encode conditional logic paths.

These findings demonstrate that the albumen colloid can represent and compute a diverse range of Boolean functions, from basic to compound expressions. By applying 4-bit binary sequences via voltage-encoded pulses and capturing MEA-based spatial responses, we established that logical operations such as conjunction, disjunction, and negation can emerge from the material’s properties.

This threshold-based mapping into logic expressions suggests potential applications in reservoir computing and soft logic circuits, where the system’s native dynamics are leveraged. The spatial voltage distribution across MEA electrodes highlights the material’s heterogeneous and parallel processing potential, which is advantageous for future bio-inspired computational systems.

Table 1: 10 most common Boolean expressions for the albumen colloid

Boolean Expression	Count
$\neg a \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg c \wedge \neg d$	433
$a \vee d \vee \neg b \vee \neg c$	361
$(b \wedge c \wedge d \wedge \neg a) \vee (a \wedge c \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg d)$	298
$c \wedge d \wedge \neg a \wedge \neg b$	218
$b \wedge d \wedge \neg a \wedge \neg c$	151
$d \wedge \neg a \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg c$	147
$\neg a \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg c$	113
$(c \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg d) \vee (d \wedge \neg b \wedge \neg c) \vee$	107
$(b \wedge c \wedge d \wedge \neg a) \vee (b \wedge \neg a \wedge \neg c \wedge \neg d)$	97
$b \wedge c \wedge d \wedge \neg a$	94

Figure 7: (a) Stacked normalised measured MEA output voltages of egg albumen for a 4-bit binary string. (b) Waterfall plot of the normalised measured MEA voltages. The spatial distribution of the voltages described by the y -axis electrode number shows the spatial complexity of the material.

4. Conclusions

Here, we demonstrated that egg albumen, a protein-rich and environmentally friendly material, exhibits memory characteristics as evidenced by frequency-dependent I–V hysteresis loops and synaptic-like potentiation and depression behaviours. Leveraging these properties with a custom-designed experimental setup and microelectrode arrays, we successfully extracted and analysed 4-bit Boolean logic operations directly from the colloidal system. Our results identify albumen colloids as promising candidates for sustainable and biodegradable computing applications, particularly in ultra-low-power bio-inspired hardware systems.

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